

Transferable Skills – Report 1

Deliverable 2.6

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.6 Transferable Skills – Report 1
Version 2

Authors:

Karim Hadjri (USFD)

Krzysztof Nawratek (USFD)

Version	Date	Authors
0.1	14.12.21	Karim Hadjri, Krzysztof Nawratek (USFD)
0.2	21.12.21	Karim Hadjri, Krzysztof Nawratek (USFD)
0.3	3.2.22	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
0.4	8.2.22	Karim Hadjri, Krzysztof Nawratek (USFD)
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Executive summary

This document describes the content and implementation process of the Transferable Skills 1 (TS1) course. It presents the course aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, and outputs. This course is focused on personal qualities and self-management, ethics, open science and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Transferable skills covered under TS1 include five topics contained in two sub-groups: (a) Personal qualities and self-management; and (b) Ethics, open science and IPR. TS1 is a 4-ECTS course, which equates to approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work.

The document also presents the results of the course evaluation in three settings: at Workshop 1, Summer School 1, and overall. There are three Annexes to illustrate the feedback from ESRs on Task 1, sample feedback to ESRs on Task 2, and the final survey results for TS1.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to document the Transferable Skills 1 (TS1) course in terms of aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, and outputs. TS1 is focused on personal qualities and self-management, ethics, open science and IPR. Transferable skills covered under the TS1 module includes five topics organized in two sub-groups: (a) Personal qualities and self-management; and (b) Ethics, open science and IPR.

TS1 is worth 4 ECTS, approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work.

This document will also present and review the evaluation of the course by the participant early-stage researchers (ESRs), which will be important in the preparation of the content and preferred type of learning activities for future courses namely, TS2 and TS3.

2. Course aims

TS1 is one of three transferable skills modules which jointly aim to foster personal qualities, entrepreneurship and professional career and communication, engagement and impact. The contents of this module are based on the UK Research Development Framework¹:

- Personal qualities and self-management: Personal qualities refer to enthusiasm; perseverance; integrity; self-confidence; self-reflection; and responsibility. While self-management is about preparation and prioritisation; commitment to research; time management; responsiveness to change; and work-life balance.
- Ethics, open science and IPR: these fall under Professional Conduct which includes health and safety; Ethics, principles and sustainability; legal requirements; IPR and copyright; respect and confidentiality; attribution and co-authorship; appropriate practice.

TS1 has the following learning aims:

1. To develop ESRs' transferable skills and introduce them to the challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
2. To develop skills in research conduct and self-management.
3. To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.

3. Learning outcomes

On the successful completion of the TS1 module, the ESRs were expected to demonstrate the following outcomes:

¹ <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

Personal qualities and self-management:

- Ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.
- Awareness of personal qualities and a willingness to demonstrate them.
- Awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.
- Ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.

Ethics, open science and IPR:

- Understanding of data ownership and management rules.
- Understanding the value of research outputs, sharing and impact.
- Knowledge of IPR policies and procedures.

4. Course structure

Figure 1 shows the timeline for the TS1 course, the links with the start-up week in July of 2021, and other network activities, as well as the sessions of RMT1 course which ran in parallel to TS1.

Figure 1. TS1 course structure as integrated with the network activities

	<p>Research conduct and ethics when dealing with human participants. You can use case studies and/or previous experiences to illustrate your arguments. 15 minutes' presentation per group.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminar session to present Task 1 on 7.9.21 <p>Task 2: Essay</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1 to critically review some of the topics covered as part of TS1, and discuss how these will influence individual research project. • Submission of Task 2 on 1.10.21 	
<p>23.7.21</p> <p>14:00 – 15:00</p> <p>15:30 - 16:30</p>	<p>Session 2: Seminar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being a researcher: Seminar will discuss individual research motivations and approaches in a context of: Mariam Attia & Julian Edge (2017) <i>Be(com)ing a reflexive researcher: a developmental approach to research methodology</i>, <i>Open Review of Educational Research</i>, 4:1, 33-45 discuss ethics and power relationships between researcher and researched individuals / groups in the context of: M. Ariel Cascio & Eric Racine (2018) <i>Person-oriented research ethics: integrating relational and everyday ethics in research</i>, <i>Accountability in Research</i>, 25:3, 170-197 	Krzysztof Nawratek
<p>26.8.21</p> <p>10:00-12:00</p>	<p>Session 3: Seminar</p> <p>Academic writing to support Task 2.</p>	Karim Hadjri
<p>7.9.21</p> <p>10:00-13:00</p>	<p>Session 4: Task 1 presentation</p> <p>Group work presentation.</p>	Krzysztof Nawratek Karim Hadjri
<p>24.9.21</p> <p>Workshop 1</p>	<p>Session 5: Mini-lectures</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personal qualities and self-management. KH 2. Ethics and data management. KN 3. Open science and IPR. KN (Open Science). KH (IPR) 	Krzysztof Nawratek Karim Hadjri
<p>19.11.21</p> <p>Summer School 1</p>	<p>Session 6: Cases of formative research projects</p> <p>Panel discussion with invited researchers (outside RE-DWELL) on 'game changing' research projects.</p> <p>Invited speakers to discuss ethics and innovative research. Speakers: Professor Renata Tyszczyk; Associate Professor Agata Justyna Twardoch; Dr Una Lynch. Moderator: Karim Hadjri</p>	Krzysztof Nawratek Karim Hadjri

The course was delivered in a blended learning format; a combination of asynchronous and synchronous (on-line and in-person) learning opportunities. This included online lectures, seminars and workshops using Miro board. In addition, there was an in-person session during the Workshop in Lisbon. The course design and delivery were affected by the Covid-19 restrictions during 2020-21, and participation and activities were implemented online. However,

course engagement turned out to be very successful. The course delivery was coordinated with colleagues leading RMT1 to avoid session clashes and excessive workload for the ESRs.

TS1 is worth 4 ECTS, approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work (Table 2).

Table 2. Typical TS1 delivery

Events	Course	Workshop 1	Summer School 1
	50 hours (2 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)
Online lectures	3	x	x
Online seminars	4	x	x
F2F lectures	x	2	x
F2F workshops	x	2	x
Presentations	3	x	x
Hybrid Panel session	x	x	3
Tutorials	x	1	1
Independent learning (80%)	40	20	21
Actual total hours	50	25	25

There were four main learning components in TS1:

1. On-line lectures
2. On-line seminars
3. In-person lectures at WS1
4. Online panel discussion at SS1

These course materials, including recordings, are available in MS Teams:

- Course descriptions
- Recorded Lectures
- Resources
- Sessions
- Tasks

5. Learning activities

TS1 included online lectures and working sessions, live seminars and workshops which took place in July and August and at the Summer School in Nicosia (November) and in-person teaching during the Lisbon Workshop (September).

TS1 training and learning activities were as follows:

5.1. Session 1: Introductory mini-lectures (16.7.21)

The online lectures were first part of the TS1 course and were delivered synchronously via Teams. They covered four areas:

1. The challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
2. Research conduct and self-management.
3. Ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging participants: Participants' rights.
4. Data ownership and management rules.

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' transferable skills and introduce them to the challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
- To develop skills in research conduct and self-management.
- To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with participant engagement and data management.

Learning outcomes:

- Ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.
- Awareness of personal qualities and a willingness to demonstrate them.
- Awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.
- Ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.

Group learning activities:

- To explore motivation for conducting research?
- To identify and discuss responsibility in research conduct?
- To discuss self-management skills and how these can be improved.

Group discussions:

- Why do you want to conduct research?
- What do you hope to achieve by conducting your research?
- How are you going to measure the success of your research?
- How do you keep yourself motivated?
- Which research conduct principle do you feel is most challenging and why?
- What support would you need in order to improve your self-management skills?
- How could your research harm various participants in your research?
- How could your research harm others or their interests?
- How do you plan to protect participants and yourself against any harm?

The sessions used a combination of mini lectures and group activities to answer specific questions related to the topic as illustrated in Figure 2.

The session also provided the opportunity to complete and agree on group formation for independent work Task 1.

Figure 1. TS1 Session 1 group activity in Miro

5.2. Independent work (16.7.21-1.10.21)

Task 1: Group work

ESRs were asked to explore and discuss (a) the challenges and opportunities of conducting research, and (b) Research conduct and ethics when dealing with human participants. They were also encouraged to use case studies and/or previous experiences to illustrate their arguments. 15 minutes' presentation per group.

Seminar session to present group work Task 1 on 07.09.2021.

Task 2: Essay

ESRs were asked to write a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1 with the aim of critically reviewing some of the topics covered under TS1, and discussing how these will influence individual research project.

Submission of Task 2 on 01.10.2021.

5.3. Session 2: Seminar (23.7.21)

The online seminar was delivered synchronously via Teams. It covered two topics:

1. Being a researcher.
2. Being researched.

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' transferable skills and introduce them to the challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
- To develop skills in research conduct and self-management.
- To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.

5.4. Session 3: Seminar (26.8.21)

The online seminar was delivered synchronously via Teams. It was dedicated to develop academic writing skills.

Learning aims:

- To develop skills in research conduct and self-management.
- To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.

Learning outcomes:

- Ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.
- Awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.
- Ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.

Group learning activities:

- Essay planning.
- Essay workflow.
- Argument development.

Group discussions:

- How do you normally plan your essay in terms of structure, content and word count?
- What are the challenges that you face when planning your essay?
- How do you decide on your essay writing process? What milestones do you use?
- What tips can you share on essay workflow?
- How do you build your argument? What strategies do you use?
- What are your views on the building blocks?

ESRs were asked to produce a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1 components delivered at the various sessions. The essay had to critically review each topic covered and discuss how these would influence their individual research project. The essay was assessed by two members of the Supervisory Board.

A seminar was organised to support the writing of Task 2. It focussed on academic writing via the use of templates and engagement in Miro board. ESRs were asked to complete the provided templates before the session. These templates provide tools for essay planning, essay workflow, and the building blocks of an argument. ESRs were also introduced to logical fallacies and a glossary for instruction words commonly used in academic English.

The seminar led to group activities to answer specific questions related to academic writing as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. TS1 Session 3 activity in Miro

5.5. Session 4: Task 1 presentation (7.9.21)

ESRs were given time to work on Task 1 as a group, and to prepare for their presentations on September 7, 2021. Five groups were created with three ESRs in each. ESRs were encouraged to reflect on their personal experiences in conducting research such as ethics, involving human participants and data management. Each group focused on different issues:

- Group 1's contribution included ethical challenges and opportunities about how to implement WFD in Hungary, analysing the behaviour of Faroese people in connection with whaling, investigation of integration and segregation amongst Catholic and Protestant university students in Belfast, and participatory design project in Dorfladen. The three ESRs then produced a mapping of shared insights (Figure 5).
- Group 2 presented their perspectives on the ethical issues that emerged while conducting research with human participants and discussed how to be critical and reflexive when drawing conclusions from personal experiences. This included qualitative research on sleeping facilities for asylum seekers, housing association dataset and GDPR, participatory design on the co-creation of a public space, and empirical observation and neighbourhood commons. They provided a mapping of keywords on the ethical concerns based on their four case studies (6).
- Group 3 addressed the issue of interaction with human participants in research and live projects, such as interviewing slum inhabitants and dealing with hostile interviewees. They synthesised their perception into an attitude of either being resilient or rigid (Figure 7).
- Group 4 produced a very informative and complex mapping of their ethics experiences and their challenges and opportunities. They also provided some useful examples of ethical concerns, and summarised their thoughts and experiences in terms of tools to implement for person-oriented ethics (Figure 8).
- Group 5 discussed navigating consent with vulnerable human participants through field experiences, the challenges of conducting research as input vs output, how to translate complex set of data, and data simplification. Their reflection includes the care needed when dealing with human participants, visualisation as a powerful tool, and data as a sensitive subject (Figure 9).

Figure 5. Group 1 shared insights

Conclusions

Fig.2: Mapping the keywords of the ethical concerns based on four case studies

Figure 6. Group 2 mapping

Figure 7. Group 3 reflection on attitude

Figure 8. Group 4 proposed tools

Figure 9. Group 5 three key lessons

5.6. Session 5: Mini-lectures (24.9.21) (Lisbon Workshop)

The workshop provided an opportunity for face-to-face interaction for the first time during the project, which proved to be both productive and enjoyable. It consisted of three one-hour sessions (a) Personal qualities and self-management; (b) Ethics and data management; (c) Open science; and (d) IPR, were delivered including group work and then followed by a 45 minutes Q&A session.

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' transferable skills and introduce them to the challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
- To develop skills in research conduct and self-management.
- To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.

Learning outcomes:

- Ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.
- Awareness of personal qualities and a willingness to demonstrate them.
- Awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.
- Ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.
- Understanding of data ownership and management rules.
- Understanding the value of research outputs, sharing and impact.
- Knowledge of IPR policies and procedures.

Group learning activities:

- Fishbone/cause and effect exercise.

The session included mini lectures and group activities to answer specific questions related to the four topics below and as illustrated in Figure 10.

- Lecture 1: Personal qualities and self-management.
- Lecture 2: Ethics and data management.
- Lecture 3: Open science.
- Lecture 4: IPR.

Friday 24 September 2021. CET time:

09:30: Welcome and introduction to the session.

09:40: Lecture 1: Personal qualities and self-management. [KH]

10:00: Activity in-person and on Miro board. 10 mins

10:10: Discussion. 10 mins.

10:20: Lecture 2: Ethics and data management. [KN]

10:40: Activity in-person and on Miro board. 10 mins.

10:50: Discussion. 10 mins.

- 11:00: Break. 15 mins
- 11:15: Lecture 3: Open Science. [KN]
- 11:35: Activity in-person and on Miro board.
- 11:45: Discussion.
- 11:55: Lecture 4: Intellectual Property Rights. [KH]
- 12:15: Discussion & Concluding remarks.
- 12:30: End.

Figure 3. TS1 Workshop 1 session

5.7. Session 6: Cases of formative research projects (19.11.21) (Nicosia Summer School)

The last part of TS1 was a panel discussion during the Summer School in Nicosia. Three speakers were invited to discuss 'Innovative research in sustainability and the importance of ethics in research'. The invited speakers were:

- Professor Renata Tyszczyk, Chair in Architectural Humanities, School of Architecture, University of Sheffield, UK.
- Associate Professor Agata Justyna Twardoch, The Silesian University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture, Department of Urban and Country Planning, Gliwice, Poland.
- Dr Una Lynch, Director of Sonrisa Solutions Limited, Banbridge, Northern Ireland.

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' transferable skills and introduce them to the challenges and opportunities of conducting research.
- To enhance ESRs' ethical sensitivity and awareness and to prepare them for ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.

Learning outcomes:

- Awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.
- Understanding of data ownership and management rules.
- Understanding the value of research outputs, sharing and impact.

The agenda was as follows:

09:00	Welcome and introductions
09:10	Introduction to topics of the round table (KH & KN)
09:30	Brief position statements from invited speakers (20 minutes each)
10:30	Break
10:45	Q&A session led by ESRs [Facilitator: ESR5 Mahmoud Alsaeed]
11:30	Closing remarks
12:00	End

Professor Tyszczyk presented a summary of research portfolio such as Provisional cities, Stories of change, Scenarios, and Rehearsal space. Some of this work explored the past, present and future of energy, sustainable development and climate change.

Dr Twardoch presented a summary of her work on housing research in architecture, highlighting contemporary trends in housing development, and the challenges of data access and comparison. She also provided examples to illustrate research with local authorities, including challenges and threats. Dr Twardoch also reviewed an investigation and analyses of five selected examples and provided a summary of lessons learnt from this exercise.

Dr Lynch discussed ageing related research and the need to protect the dignity of participants and help them to voice their opinions. She also highlighted the challenges of social isolation especially during the ongoing pandemic. She provided some examples such as the Mario project in terms of evidence of ethical claims and concerns.

The presentations were followed by Q&A facilitated by an ESR. This led to a fruitful dialogue between ESRs and the guest speakers (Figure 11).

Figure 4. TS1 SS1 Panel Discussion

Some of the questions raised by ESRs were concerned with the value of prototyping scenarios and whether testing of assumptions needs a script for action; ethics and the danger of false hopes amongst participants; quality of life of residents particularly older people and the role of neighbourhood design; the balance between indicators and reality in dealing with housing data in a holistic approach; the recognition of justice in climate emergency, and whether scenarios include vulnerable at-risk groups; the challenges of analysing mix data for housing retrofit projects; and finally concerns about energy transition.

5.8. Task 2: Essay submission

ESRs were asked to write a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1. The aim was to critically review some of the topics covered under TS1, and discuss how these will influence their individual research project.

Titles for the submitted essays are as follows:

- Self-management within research: From the micro to the macro level
- Research Ethics and Intersectionality
- The baker allergic to flour: a personal reflection on self-management
- Research data management and building information management: Exploring comparable practices
- Between good intentions and accidental exploitation: Research and data misuse
- Transferable skills as essential skills for a successful research career
- The habitus of a transdisciplinary researcher
- Ethics and sustainable development research
- Be(com)ing a participatory action-oriented designer/researcher: on ethics, binary fallacies, and entanglements
- Ethical challenges and unintentional reproduction of power structures
- Abduction within housing research: How to build trust and shared knowledge
- Opportunities for transdisciplinarity; embedding critical theory in the analysis of policies for the transition to a low-emissions built environment
- Research ethics in community-based participatory research: Being an outsider
- Challenges and opportunities when incorporating everyday ethics in social value evaluation

A good range of topics critically addressed ethics, intersectionality, transdisciplinarity, research methods, data management, and engagement with research participants. Essays were generally well-written using very good academic English and conventions (please see sample feedback in Annex 2 – Task 2 feedback).

6. Resources

Resources to support the course were provided via MS Teams folders.

Task 1:

- European Research Council (ERC) (2018) ERC DMP summary document listing FAIR data and resources. DMPonline service.
- The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (2018) Eurodoc Report: Identifying Transferable Skills and Competences to Enhance Early-Career Researchers Employability and Competitiveness. Brussels. (Accessed at <http://www.eurodoc.net>)
- Careers Research and Advisory Centre (CRAC) Limited (2010) Researcher Development Framework: Vitae (Accessed at www.vitae.ac.uk/rdf)

Task 2:

- Academic writing resources accessible at the University of Sheffield.
- Templates from the University of Sheffield about:
 - Conventions for academic writing.
 - Argument development.

- Essay writing process.
- Essay planning template.
- Essay workflow.
- Essay instructions words.
- Logical fallacies.
- Harvard referencing guide.

Other key web resources:

<https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/apse/apo/quality/policies-guidance/ip>

https://ec.europa.eu/info/business-economy-euro/doing-business-eu/intellectual-property-rights_en

https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en

7. Outputs

As described in Section 5, ESRs were to do three tasks which led to the following outputs:

Task 1: Group work. (a) The challenges and opportunities of conducting research; (b) Research conduct and ethics. Submission and presentation date on 7.9.21

Task 2: Essay. ESRs were required to produce a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1 components delivered at the various sessions. ESRs were asked to critically review each topic covered under TS1 and discuss how these will influence their individual research project. Submission date on 1.11.21

Supervisors' feedback on these two tasks is presented in the annexes.

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the TS1 course in three contexts: in the Workshop in Lisbon, the session on transferrable skills; in the Summer School in Nicosia, the roundtable was followed by questions and answers, and the evaluation of the course as a whole. The highlights of each evaluation are presented next; Annex 3-Evaluation survey contains the full evaluation results.

Workshop 1 (Lisbon):

As presented in Deliverable 3.1, the workshop was evaluated by 15 participants through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the workshop and to identify areas needing improvement. The online survey was completed by 13 ESRs and 4 super-visors/co-supervisors, resulting in a response rate of 63%. It included question about the TS1 session (Table 3).

Table 3. Survey results for Workshop 1

Questions	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Please evaluate Transferrable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4,33	4,25	4,29

Some positive feedback included:

“Relevant to see what Re-dwell can do for us, interesting to hear about the book”.

“Very informative and engaging session that stretched the limits of the course and inspired knowledge-sharing among ESRs experiences outside the course”.

“Very interesting topics and important for our research, as always at the TR sessions”.

ESR mentioned the following:

“Great work, hope to see more practical being matters being addressed: how to divulge our own research for example, opportunities for fora to discuss our work. You know let's get re-dwell to the New European Bauhaus or the Venice Biennale”.

“Personally, I find the 30min talks a bit limited. I feel that I would like to have more in-depth talks but it could be that this is my personal perspective”.

Summer School 1 (Nicosia):

The survey was evaluated by 16 participants through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the Summer School and to identify areas needing improvements.

In relation to TS1, there were 13 responses (Table 4):

Table 4. Survey results for Summer School 1

Questions	Answers	Average
Please evaluate Transferable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	3.77

Some positive comments:

“Very interesting. Great mix of guests, different approaches, research into the topics that we investigate. It's important that the professors (supervisors/ co-supervisors) involve the network of experts that they already know, so that we reach out to them.”

“It was a great idea to have guest speakers as in the roundtable, they offered complementary approaches to the topics treated throughout the seminar. For me, it was particularly interesting the presentation about abandoned housing stock assessment in Poland, and the approach used that mixed quantitative and qualitative methods.”

There was one critical comment though which contradicts the above. The TS1 team does not feel this is a fair reflection of the speakers' profiles and their respective presentations.

“The quality of the speakers was very low some of the speakers did not have clear points to make and never clarified any questions, others stumble over their words and presentations, in general very superficial.”

Overall course evaluation:

TS1 was evaluated by all 14 ESRs through an anonymous online survey (Table 5). The aim was to evaluate their experience attending and participating in the various activities of TS1 and to identify areas needing improvements to inform the development of TS2. See Annex 3- Evaluation survey for full survey results and responses.

Table 5. Survey result for the course

Questions (rating from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	Answers	Average
How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the TS1 course?	14	4.21
SESSION 1 (Online seminar, July 16)	14	3.71
SESSION 2 (Online seminar, July 23)	14	4.07
SESSION 3 (Online seminar, August 26)	14	3.86
SESSION 4 (Lisbon lectures, September 24)	14	3.86
SESSION 5 (Nicosia Panel, November 19)	14	3.5
You are expected to demonstrate ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.	14	3.64
You are expected to demonstrate awareness of personal qualities and a willingness to demonstrate them.	14	3.50
You are expected to demonstrate awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.	14	3.71
You are expected to demonstrate ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.	14	3.21
You are expected to demonstrate understanding of data ownership and management rules.	14	3.86
You are expected to demonstrate understanding of the value of research outputs, sharing and impact.	14	3.93
You are expected to demonstrate knowledge of IPR policies and procedures.	14	3.93

All comments are included in Annex 3.

The following conclusions for future courses can be drawn from the responses:

- Continue to use Miro board.
- Rotate break-out rooms for group activities.
- More exercises like the Fishbone one.
- Consider applying content to ESRs own topics.
- Provide more in-depth material. Maybe some longer presentations.
- Consider support for Ethical application and more information on Intellectual Property Rights.
- Spend more time on some topics and connect to researcher's/tutor's experience.

- Provide tips for PhD writing skills and examples.
- More open discussion, exchange of information with other PhD students especially from ITN network
- A bit more cooperation with the ESRs to see the specific needs for the upcoming classes.

Annex 1 – Task 1 feedback

RE-DWELL TS1 course Task 1 presentation - Tuesday 7 Sept. 2021

Task 1 required ESRs to explore and discuss:

- The challenges and opportunities of conducting research, and
- Research conduct and ethics when dealing with human participants.

The feedback give to ERS is compiled in the Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Feedback to Task 1

Group	The challenges and opportunities of conducting research (content; clarity; relevance; position; examples; future)	Research conduct and ethics when dealing with human participants (content; clarity; relevance; position; examples; future)	Presentation (type, quality, time)
Annette, Anna, Leonardo	<p>Anna’s experience on ethical challenges and limitations is very useful and highlight the risks. Her example of an opportunity on whale slaughter is also touching and her approach to mitigation is helpful. Informing the participants was also useful.</p> <p>Annette’s example on Northern Ireland (segregation) and the challenge of collecting data and local sensitivities is very informative. Her approach to data collection is useful and efficient. There were clear challenges and opportunities when collecting data. Good lessons there.</p> <p>Leonardo’s example on Dorfladen is very useful highlighting a real-life scenario. Useful description of the project, maybe a bit long. The position of researcher as an outsider helps understand the opportunities and lessons. Useful example of user engagement and co-design.</p> <p>Excellent synthesis of the 3 projects/experiences; e.g. patterns of research engagement and contextual nuances.</p>	Q&A: dealing with sensitive information.	<p>Anna could have used more illustrations.</p> <p>Annette: good use of information and illustrations.</p> <p>Leonardo: good combination of visuals.</p>
	<p>Anna’s experience on ethical challenges and limitations is very useful and highlight the risks. Her example of an opportunity on whale slaughter is also touching and her</p>		<p>Anna could have used more illustrations.</p>

	<p>approach to mitigation is helpful. Informing the participants was also useful.</p> <p>Annette's example on Northern Ireland (segregation) and the challenge of collecting data and local sensitivities is very informative. Her approach to data collection is useful and efficient. There were clear challenges and opportunities when collecting data. Good lessons there.</p> <p>Leonardo's example on Dorfladen is very useful highlighting a real-life scenario. Useful description of the project, maybe a bit long. The position of researcher as an outsider helps understand the opportunities and lessons. Useful example of user engagement and co-design.</p> <p>Excellent synthesis of the 3 projects/experiences; e.g. patterns of research engagement and contextual nuances.</p>		<p>Annette: good use of information and illustrations.</p> <p>Leonardo: good combination of visuals.</p>
Andreas, Zoe, Tijn	<p>Ethical issues: personal experiences, being critical through case studies and be reflexive, then mapping keywords. Word cloud informed the analysis. Tijn talked about his field research on sleeping facilities for asylum seekers. Very sensitive topic at the time. Interesting lessons learned such as with explicit consent, communication. The second example on GDPR is current and an important aspect of research and stakeholder engagement, also useful for the secondments. Zoe's case study on participatory design and challenges of access to place and participants in real life and the conflicts that emerge as a result of interaction are incredibly interesting and good lessons for others. Building trust for co-creation and clarity of project objectives are critical. Andreas' case on empirical observation is very interesting in terms of level of engagement with place and people, with or without consent (some more information on consent and boundaries would have been useful). Some good lessons on consent.</p> <p>Synthesis/mapping chart is very helpful. Use of qual and quant research with human participants. Lessons learned also very helpful such as contextual issues.</p>	<p>Q: consent, not always needed to process data.</p> <p>Can we use an implied consent such as for photos?</p> <p>Implied consent can be problematic.</p>	<p>PPT</p> <p>Good illustrations. Very clear presentation.</p> <p>Good synthesis.</p>
Christophe, Aya, Effrosyni	<p>Interacting with human participants. Interesting and engaging anecdotes. Christophe's hostile</p>	<p>Q: role of researcher/architect in aims and ethical approaches needed.</p>	<p>Miro ppt.</p> <p>Clear and very well presented.</p>

	<p>participants... is very interesting and sheds some light on language issues... cultural sensitivities, difficulty to engage participants, and preparing for interviews.</p> <p>Aya's example interviewing slum inhabitants provides lessons for conducting research in challenging potentially dangerous environments. But useful in understanding people's needs and best approach to engage with them.</p> <p>Phrini's example on design-build course, co-design with local community has its own challenges and resistance from various actors. Methods used to address this are very interesting and useful to other designers/researchers.</p> <p>Final thoughts highlight preconceptions as a critical aspect which needs to be address at the outset (very helpful). The importance of being resilient in attitude. Some interesting questions raised.</p>	<p>Value alignment? Political position?</p> <p>How do we manage uncertainty?</p>	
Saskia, Marko, Androniki	<p>Very good approach to the task; good structure and excellent analysis.</p> <p>Useful topics identified such as intersectionality and representation, ethics, time management. Autonomy as a challenge is interesting. Also identifying reactions as a challenge aligns with other groups' findings. In terms of opportunities, transfer of production knowledge is a good finding. Uncertainty e.g. funding and similarly to previous group is also a concern.</p> <p>Examples connecting challenges and opportunities and examples given are very helpful.</p> <p>Some useful examples also on data collection experiences and ethics.</p> <p>The section on ethics is impressive and quite comprehensive. Useful evaluation of relationship between participants and researchers through examples.</p>	<p>Q: approach interview questions in terms of bias.</p> <p>Reflective researcher.</p>	<p>Very good mapping and use of visuals.</p> <p>Considerable amount of information, well done.</p>

	Excellent mapping of findings and recommendations (person-oriented ethics).		
Mahmoud, Alex, Manuella	<p>Interesting account of Alex's example on navigating consent with vulnerable groups, the dilemma of seeking or not consent, and the role of the researcher.</p> <p>Manuella's experience is on quantitative research, challenges as input and output is valuable. Also the experience of dealing with complex datasets is useful.</p> <p>Mahmoud's video on topic light-hearted and amusing. Good scenario on data use and potential misuse.</p>	Use of drawings instead of photos to avoid identity exposure.	Very good presentation. Excellent illustrations.

Date: 7.9.21

Annex 2– Task 2 feedback

RE-DWELL TS1 course Task 2 feedback

ESRs were required to produce a 2,000-word essay reflecting on TS1 components delivered at the various sessions. The essay should critically review each topic covered under TS1 and discuss how these will influence their individual research project. The essay was assessed by two members of the Supervisory Board.

A sample of feedback provided to ESRs is given in Tables 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3

Table 2.1. Feedback to Task 2

	Category	Comments
1	Attention Grabber/Hook	Very relevant topic about an important personal skill and an interesting approach to discussion and strong statements. You could consider using a quotation to highlight a point.
2	Position Statement	Good articulation of the importance of self-management for wellbeing and career progression. Very good use of references to support this.
3	Support for Position	Good definition of self-management using various sources useful to support the position statement.
4	Evidence and Examples	Very helpful insight on self-management strategies such as work efficiency and the ability to manage change. The combination of macro and micro approaches helps the reader understand the value of self-management from tasks to career planning.
5	Sequencing	Arguments and references are provided in a logical order that makes it easy and interesting to follow the author's train of thought.
6	Transitions	A variety of thoughtful transitions are used. They clearly show how ideas are connected.
7	Closing paragraph	The conclusion is well-written and revisits the key points discussed. Effective restatement of the key recommendations begins the closing paragraph.
8	Sources	All sources used are credible and cited correctly.
9	Sentence Structure, Capitalization & Punctuation	Most sentences are well-constructed and there is some varied sentence structure in the essay. Author makes a few errors (typos/articles), but the essay is still easy to read.
10	Grammar & Spelling	There are some typos/articles missing.

Table 2.2. Feedback to Task 2

	Category	Comments
1	Attention Grabber/Hook	A very interesting topic on misuse of research data and tips on how to avoid it. Excellent attention grabber by highlighting the dangers of data misuse. A quotation in the introduction rather than references would have been more useful.
2	Position Statement	The position statement provides a clear statement of the author's position on the topic via observation and reflection.

3	Support for Position	Good introduction to ethics and data management. Although too much reliance on a single source (Shamoo & Resnik).
4	Evidence and Examples	Interesting examples including support strategies. Good use of hypothetical scenarios. The inclusion of personal experience is helpful and honest. This is quite detailed and very useful.
5	Sequencing	Arguments and references are provided in a logical order that makes it easy and interesting to follow the author's train of thought.
6	Transitions	Some transitions work well, but some connections between ideas are fuzzy.
7	Closing paragraph	The conclusion is well-written but is focussed on author's own research. It should have revisited the key points discussed. But the proposed steps are useful to prevent data misuse.
8	Sources	The few sources used are credible and cited correctly. More sources would have been helpful.
9	Sentence Structure, Capitalization & Punctuation	Most sentences are well-constructed and there is some varied sentence structure in the essay. Author makes a few errors (typos), but the essay is still easy to read.
10	Grammar & Spelling	There are some minor errors in grammar and typos.

Table 2.3. Feedback to Task 2

	Category	Comments
1	Attention Grabber/Hook	Good use of a quote to start the essay. The introduction is missing although the definition of habitus offers a hook to some extent. The introduction could have explained the value of habitus and mobility and how these inform transferable skills. There is no need to use bold text.
2	Position Statement	The concept of habitus is very interesting but it is not clear how this relates to self-awareness and self-reflection (reflexivity), two important personal qualities. The introduction of the concept of researcher habitus is excellent. The essay offers a very interesting philosophical approach to these topics.
3	Support for Position	There is good use of references to support arguments and definitions. The addition of transdisciplinary research aspects are very useful and offer lessons for personal research development.
4	Evidence and Examples	Most of the evidence and examples are specific including reference to the roundtable, and explanations are given that show how each piece of evidence supports the author's position.
5	Sequencing	Arguments and references are provided in a logical order that makes it easy and interesting to follow the author's train of thought.
6	Transitions	A variety of thoughtful transitions are used. They clearly show how ideas are connected.
7	Closing paragraph	The concluding part includes reflection and recommendation; this is well-written and revisits the key points discussed. Effective restatement of the key recommendations begins the closing sentence.

8	Sources	All sources used are credible and cited correctly. Good use of illustrations.
9	Sentence Structure, Capitalization & Punctuation	Most sentences are well-constructed and there is some varied sentence structure in the essay. The essay is easy to read and informative.
10	Grammar & Spelling	Grammar is fine but US spelling used (not necessarily an issue but prefer UK one!).

Annex 3– Evaluation survey

This annex contains the questions and answers to the evaluation survey.

Please evaluate the organization, content and learning outcomes of the TS1 course, and their impact on your Career Development Plan. The purpose of this evaluation is to know what worked well and what needs to be changed in the next edition of the courses.

1. COURSE ORGANIZATION

How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the TS1 course? (from 1 to 5)

Comments:

- It was well constructed.
- The content and guests could have been better curated.
- The organisational aspects were fine.
- I really enjoyed this task. While I only really learned about my personal topic (and less so the other skills), I really dug deep and enjoyed the task very much.
- Overall well organized, clear structure and clear assignments. Good to mix the different types of activities.
- The organisation of the course has been very well.
- The structure was clear and well delivered according to the schedule.
- Good.
- Lectures and talks were well-prepared. Online environment worked sufficiently.
- Overall, I think that Karim and Krzysztof did a great job with the selection of relevant literature and issues that attempted to cover throughout the seminar. Many of the aspects tackled are very relevant in the early stages of a research project and resonated with my own work.
- The content was delivered clearly, though in regards to the ethics portion, it would have been better to have additional examples from tutors in regards to how they have previously dealt with ethics issues.
- Very interesting course. Karim and Krzysztof were very informed and very passionate about the topics of the course and they really transferred this feeling to the class. Very important topics and it was helpful that we looked at these from the beginning.
- Online: I highly appreciate the use of interactive tools (Miro), and the concept of mini-lectures (maximum of 20 min slides then a practical activity) was very effective; Face to face: clear and light slides were used, the engagement with the audience was very effective as well.
- Very good workshops, online and in Lisbon.

Do you have any suggestions on how to improve the organization of the future TS courses in terms of blending of learning and types of teaching and engagement methods?

- We need presentations that have more content and engage with the issues that matter at a deeper level.
- Some more interactive exercises like the fishbone diagram would be nice and beneficial.
- Perhaps more of an integrated process regarding the different topics. For example, during one day of online sessions, we could rotate break-out rooms. The first breakout rooms each get a topic (ethics, self-management etc), then we rotate and teach one another about the other topic. I say this because I now know a lot about ethics, and not much about the other transferable skills.

- Maybe a focus on certain key elements would be more helpful than the broad depiction we got in the course (though it may be limited by the way the GA is organized of course).
- The structure of seminar followed by ESRs' collaboration (during the course time), followed by discussion has been proven a very engaging process.
- It would be beneficial to elevate our Miro Boards to a research tool. e.g. After each course to seek for patterns and translate our thoughts into metrics or even change the structure of Miro from a 'question-response' format to more mindmap format.
- I prefer the online sessions where they are recorded so we can get back to it
- Perhaps other interactive methods than just discussion would be interesting, such as polling and word cloud generation.
- Keep up the round-table style dynamic implemented for the summer school in Nicosia. It was quite refreshing to have guest speakers that offer complementary perspectives to the topics treated.
- Some of the content could have been better applied to our own topics.
- I would like more in-depth material. Maybe some longer presentations, some guests-specialists on a topic that would give a talk or pdfs and paper to read after the class, in order to really get the essence of some terms-methodologies-skills.
- Keep using mini-lecture principles.
- Perhaps orientation to the topic could be stronger during the online workshops, i.e. in online Nicosia workshop the title was ethics. I could be wrong in remembering, but feels like it was not really about ethics.

2. COURSE CONTENT

How would you evaluate the following sessions (from 1 to 5):

Session 1 (Online seminar, July 16)

- The challenges and opportunities of conducting research
- Research conduct and self-management
- Ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants
- Data ownership and management rules

Comments:

- Difficult to relate to without examples and lacked theoretical background to bring ESRs at the same level.
- Nice introduction to the researchers' transferable skills. The content was a useful food for thought especially when ESRs used Miro to express our own reflections.
- Too much information in a short time.
- A bit superficial, but difficult to cover all those subjects in-depth.
- A very much needed introduction to crucial aspects that every researcher should bear in mind when conducting research.
- Set a good tone in stressing the need for a balanced work-life ethic/quality of life, particularly at the beginning of the PhD where the role is unfamiliar and slightly overwhelming.
- Very nicely organised, very interesting topics. Maybe I would like more detailed information about some of the concepts. Sometimes I was feeling some things were only mentioned and there was no more further explanation/ discussion.
- Well-structured session that helped us understand the basics of challenges. Perhaps overall individual "grading" was a bit strange as we had to do a group work, but we are evaluated only on the part that we actually presented. In our case, presented part was not the part we contributed in, but we were nevertheless evaluated on that part. Very good evaluation of the individual essay, thank you.

Session 2 (Online seminar, July 23)

- Being a researcher / Being researched

Comments:

- Good discussion but not pertinent to my project.
- Lacking theoretical background.
- This was an excellent discussion / seminar and would like more of them!
- Good strategy to use literature to discuss these two perspectives. In terms of content, maybe not the most significant input for everyone. It could have been part of another session.
- I enjoyed it and it is good to understand but it isn't directly related to my research.
- Scientific papers did not have the highest quality.
- I found this session particularly interesting because it allowed me not only to position myself as a researcher but also as a research participant. Considering that my project is involving qualitative assessment of housing projects through the views of residents, the session offered valuable discussions and takeaways.
- Useful to know that we can write in first person and in a reflexive way, and to be introduced to example articles which demonstrate this. Could inform the writing style of the thesis depending on the type of research carried out (which is still unknown) but may involve user participation.
- For me, it was very important that we had read two papers, discussed them among us, and prepared a small presentation. We really learned from reading the papers but also from discussing among us. Also listening to the others' opinions was important to understand more holistically the topics.
- Interesting concept, made us think about our approach towards proposal and future as researchers.

Session 3 (Online seminar, August 26)

- Seminar on essay writing to support Task 2

Comments:

- I already know how to write an essay, there's always room for improvement but the level of detail needs to be deeper and more demanding, this was clearly for architects who do not know how to write.
- Relevant and to the point
- I also had a follow-up session online with Karim, once I had organised my thoughts using the template. This was extremely helpful and led to a much more enjoyable / thorough essay, so thank you.
- Very useful that we had this on the agenda. Yet all of us have an idea on academic writing it is useful to share knowledge and experiences.
- At this point of everyone's research, it might have been more useful to write a 'peer review' of given papers to see different styles of writing and argumentation building rather than write our own essay.
- The most important and useful session of the whole course. It helped a lot in writing the essays.
- I was hoping for a bit more in-depth essay instructions rather than just information about the basic structure.
- Good exercise, especially for the ones that are not very skilful or experienced in the art of writing academic literature.
- Useful to go over the basics as it had been several years since I had last written academic writing and essays, so this was a useful recap.

- Very important skill. Absolutely essential to devote some time to how to write academically. Personally, I would like more of these practical "lessons" that we really need to have a quality PhD.

- Very good topic and tools that were given to us, we are using them when approaching essays. It was very useful in writing essays that are compulsory for the examination at my university.

Session 4 (Lisbon lectures, September 24)

- Personal qualities and self-management
- Ethics and data management
- Open Science
- Intellectual Property Rights

Comments:

- We need professors to lead with their own experiences in teaching, publishing, getting jobs in academia. Relevant to know about IPR.

- Again, seemed to be more about the ticking necessary boxes rather than explaining through examples.

- I think more might be necessary later - when preparing to request ethical approval.

- In terms of content, this session was the most important and it would have been great if it exceeded a general introduction of the concepts. It would have been really useful if the presentation referred to our host institutions (even briefly). A combined document prepared by the supervisors would be very beneficial.

- I wish there were more practical advice on self-management.

- This was very interesting and engaging, a lot of room for our questions.

- It was ok. However, I experienced some technical issues that hindered my active participation in some of the activities. The room was not suitable for remote working.

- I had the feeling the conversation was passing too quickly from one topic to the other. Very interesting topics, very nice presentations from Karim and Krzysztof but I felt that I didn't have the time to process all the information or some material to revise afterward.

- Very good and challenging, especially on open science discussion.

Session 5 (Nicosia Panel, November 19)

- Discussion on Ethics

Comments:

- There was not much discussion on ethics per se.

- The presentations were very interesting but it was not necessarily clear how all of them were structured around ethics.

- Renata presentation was confusing and it was difficult to understand its implications in real life. The other presentations were very useful.

- Interesting talks, but not much on ethics.

- A novel dynamic that I encourage you to keep for the next modules. To have guest speakers enrich the conversation and allow us to connect with the further academic/industry community.

- I did not find this session as well delivered as the previous, though this was due to the setting.

- Great session, a nice panel of guests, very educative and mind-opening discussion. Listening to experts relevant to our topics, specific examples, questions that relate to our topics.

- I don't recall being it on ethics as much as on generalities.

Please explain which sessions best met your expectations and why.

Comments:

- The Lisbon session was relevant. The others felt introductory.
- The being a researcher/being researched part was a pivotal session and for me probably the most useful and substantial one, both in terms of topic and in terms of interaction with my fellow ESRs.
- The writing workshop was the most useful because it was practical help.
- I really enjoyed the seminar where we read two papers and discussed (session 2). Extremely informative and fantastic debate. More please.
- I think the activities we had where we had to fill in with our own experience was most useful. They allowed to share on our own experience and share between people.
- The session that best met my expectations was the one on academic writing, because it provided useful knowledge on different types of writing. Furthermore, ESRs were given material provided by the University of Sheffield on argument building and vocabulary.
- Session 3. It gave us practical and tangible advice
- The Lisbon one, because the Q&A session with Karim and Krzysztof really helped us in our current trajectory.
- The introductory aspects of research ethics and conduct, the discussions about positioning ourselves as researchers, and the perspectives from guest academics were very productive and insightful.
- The first sessions delivered during the workshop and summer school were less effective, due to the environment. This was better as an online activity with digital tools and in a more visual presentation.
- Session 2 - because we came prepared, we knew what we were talking about and we had time to constructively discuss, share opinions, and build on top of the theoretical readings that we had.
- Session 5- inspiring, listening to specific examples and to relevant projects.
- Session 1 and 4 since it deals with the practice of research from ethical point of view.
- Session on task 1 since it gave us actual tools we can use in our entire careers in writing essays or papers.

Please explain in which ways has the TS1 course contributed to the development of your research?

Comments:

- It introduced me to the topic of ethical considerations and through the essay "forced" me to sit down, read, write and start forming my own stance towards ethics.
- It made me think about ethics in different ways but I will need to go into much more reading to make a strong ethics case.
- Really helped me to think about how to develop a fair project that includes challenging aspects of working with participatory methods.
- Introduction to useful topics that researchers need to take into consideration both to engage with human participants and to collaborate with host institutions. Also, useful attempt to practice academic writing.
- It gave me confidence in writing. And that it is normal to feel anxious in the beginning of a research.
- It pushed us to think again about research ethics, an essential part of academia.

- I have a sound understanding of the different protocols to consider when conducting research. I have applied already some of this to my research.
- Useful in terms of laying down the basics of writing styles, conventions, and getting used to writing essays and looking for references.
- Starting to understand what it means to research from several points of view: personal, ethical, language etc.
- Each session has its positive elements. I've learned a lot about ethics, from the basic terms to data management, which is helping me now to prepare the data management plan and ethics application at my host institution.
- All of them in different ways, perhaps the Nicosia one the least.

3. LEARNING OUTCOMES

For each of the aims of the learning outcomes of the course TS1, explain to what extent you think you have achieved it to your satisfaction and whether the knowledge acquired is useful for your research (from 1 to 5).

You are expected to demonstrate ability to engage in research and maintain enthusiasm and motivation.

Comments:

- I was able to engage in research before, I am able to engage in research now. Actually, this question is not particularly well-phrased.
- I felt that we learned what is a positive quality for a researcher to possess and what is generally good practice in terms of work-life balance in general, but these cannot apply universally to everyone. Each of us have different things to work on and I personally find it very difficult to keep my enthusiasm and motivation when I doubt myself in every little step I take.
- Enthusiasm and motivation is something that needs much personal development. Cannot be easily discussed.
- It feels a bit confusing as an expected outcome. It was very useful to discuss on the matter and the professors provided very useful knowledge, but this outcome is more like a long term goal than a short-term achievement. It is building up.
- Enthusiasm differed per session.
- I consider I have maintained high levels of motivation during the sessions, participating actively in the discussions and assignments.
- I believe I put in a considerable amount of time and effort to carry out the tasks to the best of my ability.
- I feel very motivated to engage in research.
- We are well equipped for dealing with and understanding the potential of motivational issues.

You are expected to demonstrate awareness of personal qualities and a willingness to demonstrate them.

Comments:

- Buzzwords
- Again, these are struggles that are deeply rooted in past experiences and cannot be solved through a course. Most of the time I lack self-confidence and prefer to remain out of the spotlight.
- Personal qualities come across naturally over time.
- The ones I know about, yes. Not the others that were only touched-upon for me.

- Similar to the above. This aim feels quite ambitious but the course gave valuable discussions and knowledge.
- We haven't talked much about our personal qualities, but I also didn't choose the topic in my essay. So this is partially my own choice.
- Similarly, as in the previous question, I consider that I have contributed during the sessions and assignments.
- I achieved this through working professionally and with others whilst managing my time well, through uploading tasks that have been carried out thoughtfully and well written within (and ahead) of deadlines.
- I think I need to work more on self-confidence.

You are expected to demonstrate awareness of responsibility for own project and own wellbeing.

Comments:

- I'm doing a PhD I obviously don't care about my wellbeing.
- Again this comes by experience.
- I think access to therapy would be extremely helpful.
- This is a long term goal but the course definitely helped on this direction.
- We're all very aware that finishing the dissertation is in the end our own responsibility.
- I am aware of my responsibility for my own research progress and have established the required mechanisms to assure its development.
- I have been able to manage my time well and kept to a work routine which enables me to work productively during the weekdays.

You are expected to demonstrate ability to manage own time and deadlines effectively.

Comments:

- We had to move the deadline so I'm not quite sure how that speaks to this.
- And again, time-management is tightly linked to physical and psychological well-being and this is linked to feeling motivated and enthusiastic and long story short, all these aspects are interconnected and not solvable through a single course.
- Again, cannot be taught, it is demonstrated by experience.
- Starting..
- If I am asked to evaluate myself on that and considering that we had to ask for an extension to the deadline for the course submission, it would be pretentious if I claimed that I achieved that skill.
- However if I am to evaluate the course's input, the knowledge provided was very insightful for this matter and will be in my toolbox to work on time-management.
- I would have hoped for more time management tricks and tools.
- I have managed to meet the deadlines without neglecting other obligations.
- Same as above. Though I managed well, it would have been better for the project as a whole to have had more time to develop the individual thesis project. I generally felt that the TS1 essay task took too much time, though in the future I expect to be able to write essays in less time.
- I need to work more on managing the time.

You are expected to demonstrate understanding of data ownership and management rules.

Comments:

- Useful.
- Understood the importance of this.
- I know I need to gain approval, but have yet to try - therefore, am not fully aware of the processes yet.
- This part felt slightly condensed on the structure and I would need more input in order to achieve this knowledge. The course offered a nice introduction to explore the matters on my host institution in future.
- Sufficiently covered during the sessions.
- Currently, I am aware of these issues and have acknowledged the aspects that I need to work on.
- I understand the basics, though the intricacies of how this is put into practice is still unfamiliar, though I expect I will understand this better when my project is more developed.

You are expected to demonstrate understanding of the value of research outputs, sharing and impact.

Comments:

- Not sure how the course contributed to this.
- Understood the importance of this.
- The conversation on this topic was very engaging and insightful.
- This was covered in Lisbon.
- I am aware of the importance of the dissemination of results and findings. An aspect that I think we will address as our researches develop.
- Understood, particularly with the emphasis made on the need to provide blog posts and disseminate in events etc.

You are expected to demonstrate knowledge of IPR policies and procedures.

Comments:

- This was the most useful.
- Understood the importance of this.
- I know most of this from a previous course exams.
- Undoubtedly one of the most important aspects of the course and useful that this was one of the discussed topics. I would personally need even more input on that to strengthen my knowledge.
- I am aware of the most relevant aspects considering these issues and am applying this knowledge to my research project. The seminar was quite informative in this regard.
- I understand the basics, though the intricacies of how this is put into practice is still unfamiliar, though I expect I will understand this better when my project is more developed.
- Although we have discussed the IPR, the complication in the RE-DWELL context still needs more clarification.

4. CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN

What aspects of the TS1 course could be enhanced to support the objectives listed in your Career Development Plan?

Comments:

- More hard skills: we need how to knowledge not vague statements about ethics.

- More specific content, not sure how a one-size fits all approach to projects that are so different work. In the end what it means is that the course caters to the needs of the majority (architects) and leaves others out.
- Everything related to the personal qualities, even though i don't know how this can be done in this context and I would also like to delve deeper into ethics and theories on ethics etc.
- More open discussion, exchange of information with other PhD students especially from ITN network.
- How to apply for funding.
- Maybe a bit more cooperation with the ESRs to see the specific needs for the upcoming classes?
- It would be useful if there was greater focus on the parts that relate to data management, Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights. In future the relation of these topics to everyone's institutions would benefit us even more in understanding research procedures.
- More practical advice on self-management.
- Professional skills in academia (funding, networking).
- As I mentioned before, I would like to include sessions on leadership and team management, and networking.
- It would be best to apply TS1 directly towards publishing papers, both in finding connections with other ESRs, dedicating time to writing an article and applying topics to TS1 to these. TS1 could also be used to dedicate time to preparing for group contributions to events such as the International Social Housing Festival, Helsinki which must be submitted as a group.
- Prepare and provide examples of DMP's and give some technical guidelines on how to prepare ethics plans (e.g. how RE-DWELL have designed the ethics application to the EU).
- More detailed approach to writing different types of text such as essay, paper etc.

5. SUGGESTIONS

Please provide any suggestions on the content of the future courses on Transferable Skills that you deem useful for your research project.

Comments:

- Coding is one of the key transferable skills on all the reports you've mentioned. Coding workshops would be really useful.
- If it will be called transferable skills I would suggest more emphasis on actual PhD writing skills and examples of what helps, maybe by other PhD students.
- A better focus on some specific aspects of research would have been more useful.
- All the sections covered (some more than others) were useful for our future research. The variation between the teaching methods was engaging and successful. In terms of context, some of the sessions could have been condensed in one or two sessions and have the rest focusing on everyone's institutions.
- I wish to have more practical advice regarding conducting literature review, etc.
- Perhaps more about the professional work within academia (how to get funding, how to win tenders, etc.).
- Leadership and team management. Likewise, networking and links between industry and academia.
- We be better to apply the topics more directly to our own research topics so that we are able to continue to think about and develop our individual projects. TS1 could also be better used to find synergies between the ESRs (as RMT1 has) which would help to make connections and lead to joint papers etc.

- The TS1 individual essay task was the least successful part of the course in comparison to the other tasks both in TS1 and RMT1. This is due to the lack of connection to the research topic in terms of content, in combination with the amount of time that was needed to produce the essay. I would suggest that if larger bodies of work such as essays should have a stronger connection to our individual task, whilst smaller tasks in the style of the 'connector tasks' could be on topics which are more general.
- I would like for material to study before/after the sessions so that I could understand deeper the concepts.
- Personally, the writing tasks really helped me, as it was a chance to see how I write and to have feedback. I would be interested in having more essays, connected with my topic (so I could possibly use parts of it in the future).
- To build on the existing outcome of TS1 and expand more on ethical implications especially from a practical research point of view.
- A bit more focus on tools whilst approaching writing tasks as it was very valuable.